

ISSUES OF TEACHING SPEAKING TO UZBEK LANGUAGE STUDENTS

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Abstract: this article scientifically describes the current problems of foreign language teaching in our country. Scientific opinions are concluded based on facts. The problems of education and their solutions are explained on the basis of facts. It is also stated that international standards of educational processes will be studied and put into practice. At the end of the article are conclusions and suggestions on the topic. In addition, a number of suggestions and recommendations to improve the quality of educational processes were made, and a mechanism for their implementation was developed. In covering the content of the article, the scientific works and works of various world scientists have been studied, analyzed and relevant quotations have been given. At the end of the article, all comments are summarized.

Keywords: country, subject, circle, border, language, learning, system, environment, communication, time, word, wealth, skill, qualification

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"Nowaday , lear g ad teach g a fore g la guage very mporta t. Th certa ly ot in vain. It is no exaggeration to say that perfect knowledge of foreign languages is important for our country, which is striving to take a worthy place in the world community today, because our people know very well that their great future depends on foreign partners. We need to develop a method of learning a foreign language faster, based on the national characteristics of Uzbek oc ety ad l e w th huma d g ty "(Kar mov, 1998, p. 312). Such a tro g focu o fore g languages has led to the discovery of new research in the study and teaching of English. As you know, the word is a tool for communication between people. One of the phenomena that studies word development and reproduction is the phenomenon of word formation, which is an important object for the vocabulary and development of any language.

Word formation is always studied in linguistics, along with phonetics, grammar, and lexicology. If we look at the history of linguistics, word formation, the events associated with it, as well as word formation, although the subject of the debate is clear, but the relationship of this field to other branches of linguistics, its role in linguistics is one. was unthinkable. While in many scientific works word formation is interpreted as part of grammar, in some literatures it is given as part of lexicology, and even word formation is not necessarily part of lexicology. It is well known that the field of linguistics is a wide-ranging field, and each of the existing departments requires in-depth scientific research. We know that the object of study

of general linguistics is the phenomenon of word and word-formation. The issue of word formation is important and is recognized by linguists, but interpreted differently. The role of compound words in word formation is unique.

Although a great deal of research has been done on the general classification of compound words, many of the questions in it have not yet been resolved. In recent years, however, cognitive linguistics has gained momentum as a new style and direction in linguistics. Despite the rapid development of cognitive linguistics, many of its problems remain unresolved. In particular, the cognitive properties of compound words in English and Uzbek are one of the most modern and topical problems in linguistics.

It should be noted that although initially it was intended to reveal the cognitive features of compound words in English and Uzbek in the literature, in the process of determining the level of study of the topic, it became clear that the comparative languages The cognitive properties of words have not been comparatively analyzed not only in the example of fiction, but also as an object and subject of research from a cognitive point of view in general. In view of the above, the aim of the study is not only to reveal the cognitive properties of compound words in the literature, but also to identify their similarities and differences in the analysis of cognitive properties of compound words in English and Uzbek.

Currently, the entire world community is faced with a global threat - a new coronavirus infection, which makes it necessary to completely change the way of life, revise the foundations of professional activity, develop new principles of work in a team and look for more rational ways to implement professional tasks. New realities and the educational process did not pass by. Distance learning is a set of technologies that ensure the delivery of the bulk of the studied material to students at a distance, providing for the widespread use of new information technologies. Personal computers, video and audio equipment, space and fiber-optic equipment, Internet technologies, satellite television, radio, computer communications, etc. can be used as modern telecommunication means that ensure the interactivity of learning. Of course, modern education does not have sufficient experience in using distance learning. But already at the stage of its active implementation in the educational process, it is possible to determine the main advantages and disadvantages of interactive technologies.

As in our country, in systems where a foreign language is limited only by the scope of the lesson, the time and speed at which the language is taught is important. 5-7 years to acquire knowledge of listening comprehension, speaking, reading, writing and vocabulary acquisition and to apply all these skills in a foreign language from an academic point of view correctly and flawlessly There should be a curriculum that provides for regular and effective classes. From this point of

view, a week of foreign language classes in grades 2, 3 and 4 is not enough. Language teaching, which is a natural means of both written and oral communication, requires continuity. A 7-8 year old elementary school student may not be able to master a foreign language system that is only available for 4-5 hours a week and cannot be used in their own environment. Another serious problem in language teaching is related to the methods and equipment used to teach the language [1].

When examining the textbooks used at the primary school level in public schools, it became clear that there was no connection between the components between the subjects and no connection between the units of vocabulary despite the myriad of vocabularies. In fact, every word that comes out of our mouths when we use language in every situation in life is semantically connected with what was said before or after. In the early stages of learning a foreign language, the influence of students' mother tongue characteristics can be observed.

The term "interlanguage" indicates that there is always a connection between the mother tongue in the student's memory and the other language in which he or she began to learn. Also, many aspects of language development are slow in language learning. Some features and aspects of language are learned earlier and some later. Sometimes it takes a long time to learn many seemingly simple things because of differences between languages. If a student does not have the opportunity to hear and use the language, he or she will not be able to make positive progress in learning the language and will soon forget what he or she has already learned.

Each material presented in language learning should be meaningful and the topics should be linked to each other and, if necessary, linked to what the child has learned in other lessons. In this case, foreign language teachers are required to work together and make plans together with other teachers who teach the given class. It also requires taking into account and relating each student's experience and life to the learning process. In this context, content-based models and fairy tales and songs can be used in the teaching process that are relevant to the levels of cognitive, linguistic and social development and activities in which students are directly involved. In short, given that more than half of the world's population speaks two or more languages in their daily lives, we are convinced that learning a foreign language is not a miracle. In addition, we can teach a foreign language to a student not only as an opportunity for a few people to succeed, but also so that they can keep pace with the times.

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